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Domestic Debt And Economic Wellbeing In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of domestic debt on economic wellbeing in Nigeria. In determining the effect of domestic debt on economic wellbeing in Nigeria, time series data for Human Development Index, domestic debt holdings from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), domestic debt holding from deposit money banks, and domestic debt holding from non-bank financial institutions from 1986 to 2018 were collected and analysed using Philips Perron Unit Root test, Johansen co-integration technique and error correction model. The test revealed that domestic debt holding from CBN (DDCBN), domestic debt holding from deposit money banks(DDDMB) and domestic debt holding from non-bank public (DDNBP) are related to Human development index (economic development) in Nigeria on the long run at 5% level of significance. The estimated short run dynamics with respect to Error Correction Model (ECM) also revealed that among the variables selected for the investigation, Domestic debt holding from Central Bank of Nigeria (DDCBN), domestic debt holding from deposit money banks(DDDMB) and domestic debt holding from non-bank public (DDNBP) were positively but insignificantly related to human development index. This implies that domestic debt from CBN did not significantly support growth and wellbeing of the Nigerian economy; borrowed funds holding via deposit money banks in Nigeria over the years had not been properly utilized in improving capital projects and infrastructures that would alleviate growth as well as improve economic welfare in Nigeria. Also, government funding of projects through domestic debt had experienced setbacks in such that the economy was characterized of financial leakages and corruption. Improper management of government funds was equally suspected as a factor that encouraged the poor funding and application of domestic debt to viable projects that would generate returns. To curb the menace of poor application of domestic debt, the study suggested that the government and public sector units need be accountable at every level of their operations so as to minimize the mismanagement of borrowed funds.

Keywords: Government Debt, Debt Servicing, Domestic Debt, Economic Wellbeing

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria like other countries, is striving to ensure economic progress even in the midst of low capital. As a way of achieving development goals, Nigeria resort to borrowing because of its inability to generate enough savings which could be used for investment and enhance development ensuring that there exists enabling environment for people to invest their money in other sectors of the economy (Aminu, et al., 2013). In order to raise capital internally, the government borrows from both the banking system and the non-bank financial institutions. 'The periodic report of the Central Bank of Nigeria the other day on the operations of commercial and merchant banks indicate that by the end of March 2020, the federal, state and local governments were indebted to the banking system to the tune of about 950 billion' (Guardian Newspapers, 2020). This indicates clearly that the government at all levels in the federation had not relented in borrowing in all fronts- from the banking system as well as non-bank financial institutions.

Indeed unbridled borrowing had now become a standing policy of the government to raise capital. Part of the explanation of this argument was that the income of developing countries like Nigeria was quite low

that it is hardly adequate for personal consumption; in addition, individuals in Nigeria have very low saving habit and the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic did not made it easier. As a key regional player in West Africa, Nigeria accounts for about half of West Africa's population with approximately 202 million people and one of the largest populations of youth in the world. Nigeria is a multi-ethnic and culturally diverse federation which consists of 36 autonomous states and the Federal Capital Territory in Abuja. With an abundance of natural resources, it is Africa's biggest oil exporter, and has the largest natural gas reserves on the continent.

In contrast, Nigerian domestic debt profile has been on the increase in the last few years and since rendered alarming signals. While the federal government's exposure to the banks fell slightly from about ₦132 billion in 2018 to ₦92 billion in 2019, the indebtedness by the state and local governments rose over the same period from about ₦758 billion in 2018 to ₦885 billion in 2019 (DMO, 2019). The increased borrowing by the state and local governments clearly indicates that these governments had been under intense pressure for funds to pay salaries, pay contractors as well as pension benefits, among others. This was obviously not good and in the absence of appropriate measures might result to a looming catastrophe. It was therefore important to examine domestic debt considering that Nigeria was in a state where unemployment was incredibly high and the global economic crisis is far from being solved.

Though Nigeria once made huge sales of crude oil and earned much revenue being one of the major oil producing country with 2.2 per cent of the world reserve in the early 80s, the country experienced a drop in the revenue as a result of market glut in the later 80s. But unfortunately, the spending behaviour remains unchanged (Rapu, 2003). GDP growth rate declined from 19.5 per cent to 10 per cent in the 1970s and the period 1990-1994 (Asogwa & Ezema, 2005). Hence, government resorted to borrowing to avoid economic problems like inflation. Though the highest loans were intended to help complete projects, it also led to huge debt burden totalling 1.27 billion naira by the end of 1990. The trend continued to rise both in volume and structure (that is bilateral and multilateral) (Okechukwu & Anele, 2012). Another reason for borrowing was to cushion the effect of fall in revenue with the hope to balance book as soon as revenue increased. But the borrowing continued and even at a point exceeded Gross National Income (Aminu et al, 2013).

As earlier mentioned, Nigeria had not been alone in experiencing escalating levels of government domestic indebtedness, but in comparison to other countries in Sub-Saharan Africa, Nigeria's domestic debt to GDP ratio was clearly on the high side. For the non- Heavily Indebted Poor Countries (HIPC) in sub-Saharan Africa, the domestic debt/GDP ratio averaged 23 percent between 1995- 2000, but excluding Nigeria, it dropped to 18 percent (Christenesen, 2004 cited in Asogwa, 2005). One could say the evolution of government borrowing in Nigeria could be traced back to the financial reform introduced by the colonial administration in 1958 which led to the creation of marketable public securities to finance fiscal deficit. Quoting paragraph 35 of the CBN ordinance 1958 "The Bank shall be entrusted with the issue and management of federal government loans publicly issued in Nigeria, upon such terms and conditions as may be agreed between the federal government and the Bank"

While the increase in debt has not transformed in improvement in economic indices, servicing the debt on the other hand has also reduced commitments by government towards programmes and projects that are capable of enhancing development and reducing poverty (Obadan & Ujah, 2004). Even though the intentions of the government in debt management were laudable, the country still remained heavily indebted to domestic and external creditors. Investment and growth level had also reduced drastically; hence plunging the economy into situation of high poverty and poor infrastructural facility (Udo & Antai, 2014). This study specifically focused on the effect of domestic debt on the economic wellbeing in the Nigerian economy.

Statement of the Problem

Public debt refers to the total of the nation's debts which covers debts of local and state and national governments owed to institutions, government agencies and other bodies either resident in or outside a country (Oriakhi, 2002). Domestic debt or internal debt in particular, is that part of total government (public) debt in a country that is owed to domestic lenders (that is lenders within the country).For many

years now, the country's domestic debt had been on an increase in spite of the effort being made by the government to manage and minimize its crushing effect on the economy. Nigerian domestic debt has been on the rise from N1.1 billion in 2001 to N3.2 billion in 2009 and N7.1 billion in 2013 (DMO, 2019). According to the Debt Management Office (DMO), the total external debt stands at \$27.16 billion, while domestic debt climbs to \$56.72 billion reaching a total debt profile of \$83.88 billion (N25.70 trillion) at the end of June 2019. Further analysis by analysts of the debt figures showed that federal government's external borrowing climbed \$27.16 billion, while states' including FCT is \$4.27 billion. On the domestic debt side, the federal government debt was \$43.78 billion, while the states and the FCT was \$12.94 billion as of June 2019. The researcher therefore sets out to examine the impact of rising public debt especially domestic debt on economic wellbeing in Nigeria.

Studies had no doubt been carried out in the past relating to domestic debts and its impact on the Nigeria economy. For instance Mba, et al. (2013) carried out a research that analysed the importance of domestic debt on economic growth of Nigeria using error correction model procedures following an examination of properties of the time series using unit root and co-integration test. Findings among others showed that domestic debt and credit had a significant and direct relationship with GDP and that debt servicing has inverse relationship with GDP. They suggested that domestic debt should be invested in productive sector of the economy and more specifically in the real sector and further productivity gained would be achieved in the improvement on capital project expenditure.

Ayyoub, et al (2012) also examined the impact of debt on overall GDP, manufacturing sector growth and unemployment situation in Pakistan. They used the OLS technique for the period of 1989-90 to 2009-10, and result reveals that these are actual expenditures on debt servicing which are mainly responsible for the worst situation of less productivity, increasing unemployment and less contributing manufacturing sector. The study strongly suggested reducing the expenditures, on debt servicing, to utilize the external debt on more productive expenditures, to reduce population growth rate, to control the hyperinflation, and to reduce the overall government deficit in the economy.

Anyanwu & Erhijakpor (2004) also investigated domestic debt and its impact on economic growth of Nigeria using time series data for the period, 1970-2003. Result shows that current domestic debt outstanding as a ratio of GDP has a significantly negative effect on economic growth, due largely to high implicit domestic interest rates - on average, a one per cent increase in current domestic debt outstanding as a percentage of GDP reduces economic growth by 0.38 per cent. The results also show that current domestic debt reduces economic growth mainly by lowering the efficiency of investment rather than its volume. They therefore recommended the need for Nigeria to open and improve foreign access to holdings of domestic debts so as to strengthen competition and hence reduce financial costs with the accompanying introduction of financial technology and innovation that would in turn result in higher market efficiency.

However most of these studies only estimated models that paid more attention to the effect of lagged debt components more on economic growth and less on economic wellbeing which is larger in scope. The two terms are not identical. While Economic growth refers to increases in a country's production or income per capita, Economic wellbeing is measured by material living conditions which determine people's consumption possibilities and their command over resources and quality of life; for instance, measure of literacy, life expectancy and health care. The study fills this gap by employing an econometric technique that incorporates both the levels and lagged effects. Moreover, real gross domestic product (RGDP) was mainly used to measure economic wellbeing. The global economy and GDP of many nations including Nigeria have grown consistently for years, but human wellbeing and ecological health had not kept pace. This was evident in the widespread of unemployment and poverty as well as massive inequality in the distribution of wealth among others. This study considered it a gap and saw GDP as an insufficient measure of economic wellbeing. Hence, Human Development Index was selected as the proxy for measuring economic wellbeing.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to examine the impact of domestic debt on economic wellbeing in Nigeria. The specific objectives include to:

1. examine the relationship between domestic debt holding from CBN and economic wellbeing in Nigeria
2. determine the effect of domestic debt holding from deposit money banks on economic wellbeing in Nigeria
3. examine the impact of domestic debt holdings from non-bank financial institutions on economic wellbeing in Nigeria

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between domestic debt holding from CBN and economic wellbeing in Nigeria?
2. What is the effect of domestic debt holding from deposit money banks on economic wellbeing in Nigeria?
3. What is the impact of domestic debt holdings from non-bank financial institutions on economic wellbeing in Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between domestic debt from CBN and economic wellbeing.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between domestic debt holding from deposit money banks and economic wellbeing.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between domestic debt holdings from non-bank public and economic wellbeing.

Conceptual Clarification

Government Debt

Central government debt, also known as government debt, is the total debt (bonds and other securities) of a country's government. Government debt refers to the total amount of debt of a country paying state, state and local authority debt to institutions, authorities and other entities residing in the country or abroad (Oriakhi, 2002). Often expressed as a percentage of gross domestic product (GDP), Central government debt as a percentage of GDP is often used as a measure of a government's ability to meet its future obligations. Public debt means debt incurred by a state or authority.

Debt Servicing

Tuovilla (2019) defined debt servicing or repayment as money required to pay interest and capital over a period of time. The debt service ratio is a tool used to measure a company's leverage. Central government debt often has a repayment plan. A full commitment and getting the government to follow a repayment plan is called debt repayment. In most cases, the installment plan is included in the repayment plan, and the cost of the loan, i.e. interest, is also included in the installment plan. Non-compliance with repayment schedules can be standard and can result in fixed fines. As a result, the government was unable to pay its debts (Adesola, 2009). It is therefore important to consider all types of debt instruments and debts that state and state-owned enterprises must service and repay from their income. These categories include government bonds, government bonds, central bank accounts and bills of exchange, bonds, loans, bills of exchange, treasury stocks, treasuries, delinquent payments, privatization obligations, recapitalization bonds and contingent liabilities.

Domestic Debt

Domestic debt is the portion of a country's total public debt owed to domestic creditors (i.e. domestic creditors). In other words, when the government decides to cover the deficit through available local institutions in the economy, such as banks, stock markets, etc., such funds are called domestic debt. In most cases, governments do this by issuing financial instruments such as government bonds, government instruments, and government bonds (Ozurumba & Kanu, 2014). Others include FGN bonds and

promissory notes (Abula & Modecai, 2016). Theoretically, there are three reasons for the increase in domestic public debt (Alison, 2003). The first is the financing of the fiscal deficit, the second is monetary policy (the sale of government bonds in the open market), and the third is the development of the financial sector (the provision of marketable financial products to deepen the financial market).

Economic Wellbeing

The concept of well-being is often used and is often replaced by terms such as quality of life, happiness, and even progress. However, there is no universally accepted definition of what it is. Andrews and Withey (1976) believe that well-being arises from the extent to which people perceive their objective position and their needs, desires, or values. According to this definition, Neuss (1999) believes that personal experiences or perceptions of one's life are accepted as a measure of quality of life. Economic well-being is defined as present and future economic security. Actual financial security includes the ability of individuals, families, and communities to continue to meet basic needs (including food, housing, equipment, health care, transportation, education, childcare, clothing and taxes paid) and to manage the day. It's possible. - Today's economy. It also includes the ability to make financial choices and feel a sense of security, personal fulfillment, and aspiration for employment. Future financial security includes the ability to withstand financial shocks, meet financial goals, build financial assets, and maintain adequate lifetime spam (Social Work Education Council, 2016).

Despite the lack of a single definition of well-being, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2013) argues that most professionals and lay people around the world agree on the need to meet different human needs. It's important. (eg good health) includes the ability to pursue goals, thrive, and be satisfied with life. Therefore, this study uses three pillars to understand and measure human well-being as defined in the OECD Better Lives Initiative introduced in OECD (2013). These include:

- i. Material living conditions (or economic well-being), which impact people's consumption options and resource control.
- ii. Quality of life is defined as a combination of non-monetary characteristics that determine an individual's opportunities and life chances, and it has intrinsic value in various cultures and circumstances.
- iii. The long-term viability of the socio-economic and environmental systems in which people live and work, which is critical for long-term well-being. The influence of present human activities on the stocks of various types of capital (natural, economic, human, and social) that underpin well-being is what determines sustainability.

GDP as an Indicator of Economic Wellbeing

Economic growth is the continuous growth or increase in the production of goods and services, as evidenced by an increase in the gross domestic product (GDP). Thus, while GDP was created only as a macroeconomic accounting tool, it has become the standard measure of economic development.

Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is a financial measure of the market value of all goods and services produced in a country over a period of time (usually one year). One of the biggest problems with GDP is that it does not separate costs and benefits. It is briefly described in the section on economic activity. At the individual level, economic activity is important for well-being, but when GDP per capita reaches very low levels, these relationships become very weak. In addition, the production and consumption of "valueless" goods results in a net loss of health and happiness.

Robert F. Kennedy said in his 1968 speech (Justin, quoted in 2012): We have seen the loss of natural wonders in miraculous expansion, but the gross domestic product does not take into account the health of our children, the quality of education or the enjoyment of play.

Human Development Index (HDI) as an Alternative Measure of Economic Wellbeing

The UN Human Development Report defines HDI as a statistical measure of the extent to which the development experiences of different countries contribute to the expansion of human capacities and functioning (UNDP, 1998). The concept of the Human Development Index (HDI) is far richer and more diverse than we can capture with a single economic well-being index. However, HDI is useful because it

allows us to focus on the qualitative development dimension and can affect countries with relatively low HDI scores when reviewing nutrition, health and education policies. HDI summarizes many of the social indicators in a composite index that combines three indicators: life expectancy, education and living standards.

- a. Longevity - Measured by the average life expectancy at birth (years), calculated assuming that babies born in a given year experience the current mortality rate from each age group (1st year, 2nd year, etc., to 9th year .) throughout their lifetime.
- b. Education - Education level consists of two variables. Two-thirds of body weight is based on adult knowledge (percent) and one third of body weight is based on total enrollment (percent) in compulsory, secondary and tertiary education.
- c. Standard of living - an indicator of the standard of living based on GDP per capita (UNDP, 1998).

METHODOLOGY

The ex-post factor design was considered for this study. As the name implied, the design in a easy, clear and simple way, measured and explained the cause-effect relationships that were among the variables used for the study. This study's methodological framework is based on Keynesian theory. The importance of this theory to the subject matter under examination, which is to study the effects of domestic debt on economic wellbeing in Nigeria using HDI as a proxy for measurement, was the basis for its adoption. The data used in the study were secondary in nature. From 1986 to 2018, annual time series data was gathered from the Statistical Bulletin and Debt Management Office of the Central Bank of Nigeria. Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method, Phillips Perron Unit Root test, Johansen Co-integration test, and Error Correction Method are some of the analytical or estimate approaches that were applied (ECM). The estimation methodology used a three-step modeling procedure: Data stationarity was established, and the integration order was define; Johansen co-integration test was used when the data stationarity was established. The Co-integration test was used to examine whether the variables had a long-run equilibrium connection, determining that the variables are co-integrated, the study used the ECM approach to estimate the short run dynamics. The study used HDI as a proxy for measurement and as a dependent variable to analyze the influence of domestic debt on personal income in Nigeria, while domestic debt holdings from the CBN, deposit money banks, and non-bank public were utilized as independent or explanatory factors. The model for this study is derived from the works of Peter, et al (2013) and Lotto & Mmari (2018) who examined the nexus between domestic debt and economic growth for Nigeria and Tanzania respectively. The aforementioned studies adopted domestic debt as a variable without disaggregating it to observe its specific effects on economic growth. This study therefore modifies the above models by dis-aggregating the domestic debt variable to include Domestic debt holding from CBN, Domestic debt from deposit money banks and Domestic debt from non-bank financial institutions in other to examine their various effects on economic wellbeing which is measured by human development index. The functional form of the model to be estimated is thus:

$$HDI = f (DDCBN, DDDMB \text{ and } DDNBP) \text{ ----- } 1$$

The econometric form of the model is stated as:

$$HDI = a_0 + a_1DDCBN + a_2DDDMB + a_3DDNBP + \mu \text{ ----- } 2$$

Where;

HDI= Human Development Index

DDCBN= Domestic debt holding from CBN

DDDMB=Domestic debt from deposit money banks

DDNBP=Domestic debt from non-bank financial institutions

And μ is a stochastic variable or error term, a_0 = intercept and a_1 , a_2 , a_3 are the coefficients of the regression equation.

Time series data sourced from secondary sources (Central Bank of Nigeria as well as Human Development Report Office) were used for this study. In determining the effect of domestic debt on economic wellbeing, data on domestic debt holding from CBN, domestic debt with deposit money banks,

domestic debt from non-bank financial institutions human development index (HDI) were collected from the aforementioned sources for the period 1986 to 2018. The Phillips Perron test was the choice of stationarity test. Time series data are assumed to be non-stationary and this implies that the results obtained from the OLS method may be misleading. In this vein, it was cognizant to conduct stationarity test. The stationarity test was carried out using the Phillips Perron Unit Root Test. This test makes a non-parametric correction to the t-test statistics and is robust with respect to unspecified autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity in the disturbance process of the test equation. The stationarity of data is essential for the Johansen co-integration test. The decision rule for the Phillips Perron Unit root test states that the Phillips Perron Test statistic value must be greater than the Mackinnon Critical Value at 5% at absolute term for stationarity to be established at level and if otherwise, differencing occurs using the same decision rule. Johansen test is a way to determine if three or more times series are cointegrated. It specifically assesses the validity of a cointegrating relationship using a maximum likelihood estimates (MLE). It also used to find the number of relationships and as a tool to estimating those relationships (Wee & Tan, 1997). The co-integration test was used to establish whether a long-run equilibrium relationship exist among the variables. The Johansen co-integration procedure is based on trace statistics and the Eigen value. To establish co-integration, the likelihood ratio must be greater than the Mackinnon Critical Value at 5% levels of significance and the co-integrating equation would be chosen from the normalized co-integrating coefficient with the lowest log likelihood. Co-integration is a prerequisite for the error correction mechanism. Since co-integration is established, it would be pertinent to proceed to the error correction model. The first step in ECM is developing an over-parameterized model (ECM) and then the parsimonious model (ECM 2), the Over-Parameterized Model (ECM 1) and the Parsimonious Model (ECM 2) was used. Three post-estimation tests were conducted after estimation of the model. These tests are as follows:

- i. Breush-Godfrey Serial Correlation Test
- ii. Heteroscedasticity Test; and
- iii. Cumulative Sum of Square test (Stability Test)

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Stationarity Test (Philip-Perron)

The Philip Perron (PP) test conducted on all the time series variables used in this study shows the result in table 1

Table 1: Philip Perron (PP) Result

Variables	PP Statistics @ Levels	5% Critical level	PP Statistics @ 1 st Difference	5% Critical level	Order of Integration
HDI	-2.735119	-2.957110	-7.134205	-2.960411	I(1)
LOGDDCBN	0.964554	-2.957110	-4.322295	-2.960411	I(1)
LOGDDDMB	-0.160344	-2.957110	-6.239443	-2.960411	I(1)
LOGDDNBP	7.121194	-2.957110	-3.875301	-2.960411	I(1)

Author's computation from E-views 10

Based on the above table, Philip Perron (PP) result reveals that all the variables became stationary at the 1st differencing. This implies that the series: Human development index (HDI), domestic debt holdings from CBN (DDCBN), domestic debt holdings from deposit money banks(DDDMB) and domestic debt holdings from bank public in Nigeria (DDNBP) are stationary at first differencing and therefore possesses the time series characteristics of constant mean, variance and auto-covariance upon time. The first difference integration of all the variables gives the opportunity to further apply the Johansen cointegration test to examine if the variables share mutual trend.

Johansen Cointegration Test

Having established that the level series data are of the order of 1(1), the study now apply the Johansen co-integration technique to verify the existence of long run co-integrating relationship or whether the variables share mutual stochastic trend and are linked in a common long-run equilibrium. The Johansen co-integration procedure is based on trace statistics and the Eigen value. The result is presented in table 2.

Table 2: Johansen co-integration Result

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)				
Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigen value	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.930715	141.1703	63.87610	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.648907	58.41485	42.91525	0.0007
At most 2 *	0.479920	25.96700	25.87211	0.0487
At most 3	0.167958	5.700051	12.51798	0.4993
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigen value)				
Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigen value	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.930715	82.75542	32.11832	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.648907	32.44785	25.82321	0.0058
At most 2 *	0.479920	20.26695	19.38704	0.0372
At most 3	0.167958	5.700051	12.51798	0.4993

From the Johansen co-integration outcome presented in table 2, the result of the Trace and Max-eigen value tests reveal that there are three co-integrating equations each at 5% significant level. This means that the chosen variables: human development index (HDI), domestic debt holdings from CBN (DDCBN), domestic debt holdings from deposit money banks (DDDMB) and domestic debt holdings from non-bank public in Nigeria (DDNBP) shares mutual trend and are related in the long run. Having established the long run link of the series, the investigation proceeded to estimate the short run dynamics using the ECM procedure.

ECM Results

Table 3: Error Correction Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.542833	0.010818	50.17710	0.0000
D(HDI(-1))	-0.094144	0.225401	-0.417671	0.6802
D(DDCBN(-1))	5.76E-05	5.33E-05	1.080277	0.2917
D(DDDMB(-1))	2.33E-06	2.37E-05	0.098650	0.9223
D(DDNBP(-1))	9.07E-06	4.71E-05	0.192329	0.8492
ECM(-1)	-0.547320	0.236609	-2.313188	0.0304
R-squared	0.420622	Mean dependent var		0.530000
Adjusted R-squared	0.209939	S.D. dependent var		0.050707
S.E. of regression	0.045071	Akaike info criterion		-3.123450
Sum squared resid	0.044691	Schwarz criterion		-2.707131
Log likelihood	57.41347	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-2.987740
F-statistic	1.996466	Durbin-Watson stat		1.918537
Prob (F-statistic)	0.045286			

The study have estimated the ECM which is short run dynamic mechanism for the study period 1986 to 2018 and the result from the output documented that the variable; Human development index been the dependent variable that measures economic wellbeing in Nigeria is negative and insignificant. This was observed at first differencing of the series.

Domestic debt holding from CBN (DDCBN) was positive and contributed insignificant human development index. This indicated that domestic debt holding from CBN have minimal effect on economic wellbeing in Nigeria.

Domestic debt holding with deposit money banks (DDDMB) was positively but insignificantly related to human development index in Nigeria. This further implies that Domestic debt in possession of deposit money banks has not impacted much on the development of the Nigerian economy as depicted by human development index.

Domestic debt from non-bank public (DDNBP) contributed positively but insignificantly to human development index been a measure of economic wellbeing in Nigeria. This implies that domestic debt sourced from non-bank public has shown minimal contribution to wellbeing of Nigerians.

Furthermore the ECM residual with a value of -0.547320 is significant at 0.0304. This implies that the model can correct its previous errors or disequilibrium to equilibrium at an adjustment speed of about 54%. In terms of the overall performance of the model, the fisher's statistics is significant. This implying that all the variables (Domestic debt holding from CBN (DDCBN), Domestic debt holding with deposit money banks (DDDMB)) and domestic debt from non-bank public (DDNBP) are jointly related to human development index. The Durbin Watson statistics is approximately 2 and the investigation can confidently conclude that the series are non-correlated serially. This implies that the variables in the model and the model itself are not suffering from problem of serial correlation among successive error terms.

Diagnostic Statistics

Table 4: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test

F-statistic	0.245368	Prob. F(2,20)	0.7847
Obs*R-squared	0.742425	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.6899

The null hypothesis of no serial correlation cannot be rejected in the test, since the F- statistic is not significant judging from the probability of the F-statistics which is greater than 0.05. The test is based on the null hypothesis that there is no serial Correlation. Therefore there is no evidence of serial correlation and that the model is good for policy making.

Table 5 Heteroskedasticity Test: ARCH

F-statistic	0.002305	Prob. F(1,28)	0.9621
Obs*R-squared	0.002469	Prob. Chi-Square(1)	0.9604

The heteroskedasticity test based on ARCH approach test on the null hypotheses that the errors are both homoscedastic and independent of the regressors shows that the probability of the F-statistics (0.9621) is statistically insignificant at 5%. This means that the model is free from heteroskedasticity and is therefore homoscedastic.

The study tested for the stability properties of the short-run model using CUSUM test. The existence of the parameter instability is established if the cumulative sum of the residual goes outside the area between the two critical (dotted) lines. It is estimated at 5 percent critical level. The result of the cumulative sum of recursive residual fell within the critical boundaries for the 5% significance level indicating that the model was stable.

The CUSUM of squares test is a slightly stricter test. The CUSUM of squares test gives a plot of the expected value of the test against time and the point of 5 percent critical lines. The test establishes that for the period under review, the mean value line falls within the critical lines suggesting the existence of

model stability. Therefore the Cumulative Sum of Squares of Recursive Residuals (CUSUMSQ) was within the critical boundaries for the 5% significance level indicating that the model was stable.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Pursuant to the objectives and the various hypothesis of the study, this investigation estimated the short run dynamics with respect to the error correction model (ECM) for the scope under investigation. Among the variables selected for the investigation, Domestic debt holding from Central Bank of Nigeria (DDCBN) was positively but insignificantly related to human development index. By implication, domestic debt from CBN did not significantly support growth and development of the Nigerian economy. It was suspected that most of the domestic debts borrowed from the central bank of Nigeria have not been properly utilized in financing development in the Nigerian economy in terms of infrastructures and social amenities. This may be attributable to the high level of corruption in Nigeria that had impeded development of the economy.

Domestic debt with deposit money banks (DDMB) became positive and insignificant to human development index in Nigeria. This means that borrowed funds holding via deposit money banks in Nigeria over the years have not been properly utilized in improving capital projects and infrastructures that would alleviate growth and as well improve welfare in Nigeria. The outcome of this study violated the views of Ayuba and Khan (2019), Anyanwu and Erhjiakpor (2004) who examined and conclude that economic growth and domestic debt were not related.

Domestic debt from non-bank public was also found to contribute minimally to human development index in Nigeria. By implication, government funding of projects through domestic debt had experienced setbacks in that the economy was characterized of financial leakages and corruption. Improper management of government funds was equally suspected as a factor that encouraged the poor funding and application of domestic debt to viable projects that would generate returns. To curb the menace of poor application of domestic debt, this study suggested that the government and public sector units be accountable at every level of their operations so as to minimize the mismanagement of borrowed funds. This finding would validate the outcome of the previous findings documented by Mba, et al (2019) who found that domestic credit minimally contributed to economic wellbeing in Nigeria.

With emphasis on the outcome of the results from the statistical test, its observed that the variables; Domestic debt holding from Central Bank of Nigeria (DDCBN), Domestic debt with deposit money banks (DDMB) and Domestic debt from non-bank public (DDNBP) have impact on human development index which is proxy for economic wellbeing in Nigeria. These results are basically anchored on the Keynesian theory of public financing. The Keynesian theory of public financing emphasize on mobilization of 'unemployed funds' in the private sector by the government through borrowing with the intention to boost aggregate demand, aggregate output, create jobs, but level of private consumption would remain unchanged. Abula and Mordecai, 2016) had earlier observed that when public debt is proper and judiciously utilized, it could stabilize the macro economy and also enhance productivity.

CONCLUSION

Domestic debt as an internal source of raising fund is important in myriads of ways for instance is expected to assist the economy in financing of infrastructural development and long term investment that will foster economic growth and development in Nigeria. Given the importance of domestic debt, this study has reviewed existing literature on the impact of domestic debt on Human development index in Nigeria within the scope of 1986 to 2018 and at 5% level of significance we can confidently conclude that in the long run, domestic debt holdings from CBN (DDCBN), domestic debt holdings from deposit money banks (DDDMB) and domestic debt holdings from non-bank public (DDNBP) are related to Human development index (economic development) in Nigeria. Also in the short run, the aforementioned correlates of domestic debt contributed minimally to the growth and wellbeing of the Nigerian economy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Arising from the findings of the study, the study suggests the following as recommendations:

1. Domestic debt should be channeled to productive sectors of the economy, specifically the manufacturing and industrial sectors to boost employment, as well as industrial output.
2. Government should use borrowed fund to finance capital projects such as infrastructures that will enable economic growth and development in Nigeria.
3. Government should reduce the level of domestic debt it raises over time because of its effect in aggravating the level of poverty in Nigeria.
4. Government should divest itself from all projects which the private sector can handle including refining crude oil (petroleum product) and transportation but should provide enabling environment for private sector investors such as tax holidays, subsidies, guarantees and most importantly improved infrastructure.

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